

Water Quality Management: Strategies for Conservation of Bhopal Waters

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Abstract

The city of Bhopal is crowned with lakes and reservoirs, which are major sources of potable water, recreational activities and aquaculture. These reservoirs are under great environmental stress due to agricultural run offs, human encroachments, siltation and growth of aquatic weeds. In order to maintain Upper lake as a healthy water- resource for drinking purposes, lower lake as a recreational ground for boating, water games, tourism and surface transport and Shahpura reservoir as a pisciculture station, an attempt has been made to formulate certain measures, that can cure the already spoilt lakes and check the water sheds from getting eutrophicated further.

Key words: Lake, Conservation, Restoration, Bhopal waters, Eutrophication.

Introduction

Man made eutrophication of fresh water emerged in sixties as one of the most relevant causes of water quality deterioration. Excessive enrichment of inland waters, coupled with dramatic urbanization, has led to formidable algal blooms in many parts of the world. These algal blooms are, not only believed to impair the over all quality of water but, also known to produce toxins, which when accumulate in fish, can along with food chain, be transferred to man.

Since 1980's Italy has progressively introduced legislation limiting phosphate content from 26% (1982) to just 4% (1988) in waters (Water and Environment International 1992). In South Sweden, the agricultural areas especially of Lake Rings fen ere given so much attention that in 1985, Government restricted the use of fertilizers, storage and distribution of manure and operation of sewage treatment systems (For berg 1987). Countries like USA, Sweden and Israel have taken several concrete measures to restore the already etrophied lakes but unfortunately very little information are available on suchprogrammes in India and that too on Bhopal waters. In the present communication, a few restoration measures have been explored after thoroughly consulting a number of successful examples from abroad and from the data compiled in the laboratory during last ten years. The purpose is directed to plough right through the problem practically rather than giving mere deductions.

Exploration Zone

Bhopal, the capital of Madhya Pradesh, is situated amidst Vindhyachal ranges at an altitude of 495 m above MSL. The city has a pride possession of lakes and reservoirs. Upper lake has been the lone source of drinking water to 12 lac population of the city. The reservoir is said to have been a part of much larger sheet of water that existed in the 11th century. The present stretch of 32 kms² has been resulted by impounding a seasonal rivulet Kolans. The lake is dammed at two places, the eastern end near Kamla Park and the western bank, which is surrounded by agricultural fields. Forested slopes of Shamla hills adorn the southern fringe of the lake, contributing raw sewage and agricultural runoffs. During festivals, nearly 2000 idols are immersed every year that adds to 75 tons of silt into lake. Consequently the sinuosity of lake has receded over the years. Lower lake, located in a densely populated area of the town, was created in 1749 by constructing an earthen dam across the Upper Lake. Human interventions like bathing, washing of clothes and dumping of garbage have impinged radical changes in the composition of lake water. Cultivation of lotus with a primary aim to add beauty has been causing reduction in the depth of the lake. Further, the southern arm of this lake is completely occupied by huge vegetation comprising *Hydrilla*, *Lemna* and *Azolla* in the name of *Jal Upvan*.

Shahpura lake is an elliptical receptacle situated in thickly populated southern part of Bhopal. Created due to stone quarrying activity adjacent to village Shahpura, the lake was filled up by storm water and developed into the present form. Due to inadequate catchment area, most of the impounded water contains sewage inflow, which imparts colour, odour and taste to it. Despite immense strain experienced due to extrinsic as well as intrinsic factors, the lake is serving as a pisciculture station for the Department of Fisheries, Govt. Of M.P. To save the water shed from extinction, its management has been taken over by E.P.C.O.

Thus very little attention has so far been given to these beautiful reservoirs, which offer drinking water supply and wonderful opportunities for water sports, tourism and surface transport.

Recommendations

In order to save Bhopal waters from hypereutrophy as well as propagation of obnoxious algal species, it is necessary to minimize harmful fluxes from land to water. Diversion of sewage is likely to be one of the most effective ways of checking eutrophication as nutrients input is largely derived from this source (Edmondson 1972 and Bjork 1972). In U.S.A., restoration of Lks has been successful in Lake Washington and Shangava Lake using waste water (sewage) treatment (Goldman and Home 1983). In Sweden, similar efforts were made by lowering detergents, phosphorus contents and nutrient load.

Studies conducted by Garg and Garg 1997, 1998, 1999, 2000 and 2001 on Bhoal waters under microcosmic conditions, also revealed that control of Phosphorus had a check on propagation of algal growth. In controlled microcosm, when no nutrient was added, observed that algae found it arduous to multiply obviously due to deficiency of nutrients mainly phosphorus. In treated microcosms, they flourished well, till the time; the added nutrients already present in natural waters were available. In the later days, very low abundance was determined in microcosms. Thus in order to check the entry of nutrients, in upper lake, the sewage should be immediately diverted to Biogas based sewage treatment in the northern and southern side of the lake (long pipes for sewage transport are not recommended as they are undesirable and uneconomical). In lower lake, washer men colony should be shifted away from the bank to prevent detergent in flow, which accrues hardness and phosphorus inputs to water. Shahpura Lake is being polluted by *Panchsheel Nullah*. The suspended nitrates and phosphates of the Nullah should be prevented by putting a solid masonry barrier across it so as to head up the water and then the water should be taken into sewer line by passing through a grit chamber.

Some scientists believe that nitrogen control is needed to maximize the benefits of phosphorus reduction in fresh waters. Phosphorus stimulates algal growth, which, in turn, consumes nitrogen. When phosphorus is removed,

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the algal growth stops and the unconsumed nitrogen is left as such where it is available to create even larger blooms. To overcome this situation, use of wetlands is expedient, which serve as a means of reducing the nutrient load to adjacent bodies of water (Kadlec 1987 and Kusler *et al.* 1994). It is a combination of saturated soil, plants and Microorganisms that provide aerobic and anaerobic conditions and encourages nutrient removal (especially nitrogen) from the overlying flood water (Johnston 1991). These buffer zones act as sink-preventing nitrate built up (nitrification) and in turn recycle it to nitrogen gas (denitrification) by the same mechanism. Thus, in order to remove excessive nitrogen from water, wetlands should be created in the vicinity of Bhopal lakes.

Encroachments on the water margins of lakes should be taken off and dumping grounds on catchment areas should be completely banished. Human and animal intervention should be minimized in the fringe areas by making fences and a live barrier in the form of a highway.

Introduction of grass carp *Ctenopharyngodon Idella* in 90 water systems of Sweden proved quite successful. Judicious stocking of selected fish types like *Ctenopharyngodon idella* (grass carp), *Hypophthalmichthys molitrix* (Silver Carp), *Cyprinus carpio* (Common Carp) may effectively be used as biological agents to control plankton in the ecosystem of lakes (Bhatiya *et al.* 1973 and Juanico *et al.* 1994). This indirectly curbs the growing eutrohy if proper type is selected. If planktiferous fish are massive in number, they consume zooplankton consumer fish varieties are bred in Shahpura Lake or selective zooplankton community is allowed to flourish, lake water becomes comparatively cleaner. The task already taken up by fisheries department, Govt. of Mdhya Pradesh is praiseworthy, still better varieties are to be bred and techniques improved. Besides, aquatic macrophytes are also reported to control eutrophication as they shade algal growth and assimilate nutrients released from both external and internal sources. This situation of limiting nutrients by macrophytes in open lakes has been proposed by Goel *et al.* 1985 Petr 1987 and Sen *et al.* 1992. Two species of Chlorophyceae viz *Chlorella* and *Scendesmus*, are also found to reduce nitrogen and phosphorus load from sewage water (Tam and Wong 1989) and hence can be proved effective in preventing eutrophication. In upper and lower lakes, useful plants like lotus and trapa should be sown to check the entry of nutrients, which would also serve as an additional source of revenue.

The lake waters can also be provided with copper treatment, as it is economical as well as effective to kill the floating masses. The chemical is non-toxic to fish and zooplankton and is rapidly lost to sediments. Besides, nitrate can also be reduced by carbon additions as performed experimentally in aquifer microcosms by Obenhuber and Lawrence 1991.

Bubbling and hypolimnetic aeration removes oxygen deficiency (Forsberg 1987). When nutrients diversion is not possible, excess nutrients and low oxygen in bottom waters may be altered by physical or chemical means as flushing and aeration. Trees should be planted around the three water formations to check soil erosion, siltation and flooding. Deweeding campaign should be launched for manual removal of weeds, which can be used later as compost. This step is especially needed in Shahpura lake whose 75 % of lake area is covered by weeds. In upper lake de-silting should be done at least at the shores especially from where the water enters the lake and turns towards Bhadbhada while in Shahpura reservoir, drain entering it should be cemented at both banks, up to the stream of barrier.

Process of sediments removal should be started early and huge amount of organic matter that comes out can be used for agricultural purposes in the form of fertilizers. Sign boards with slogans depicting the importance and cleanliness of water should be put all around to create / awareness. A central lake authority should be set up for periodical monitoring of lakes and implementation of schemes for lake restoration. Economic development should be promoted by bringing back aesthetic beauty and vitality.

In this direction, ministry of environment and forest, Govt. of India, has drafted a scheme for conservation and management of twin lakes of Bhopal (the upper and the lower) on the guidelines laid down at Ramsar Convention held in Egypt and a Grant worth Rs. 335 crores has been sanctioned by O.E.C.F. Japan. The project

has taken off with an aim to deepen and widen the spill channels, restoration of island, installation of fountains and improvement in the quality of water. However, to ensure the availability of potable water in increased quantity and satisfactory quality from upper lake and to preserve the aesthetics of lower lake of Shahpura reservoir, it is of vital importance to curb the entry of agricultural run offs, divert the inlets of sewage of impose a ban on anthropogenic activities in and around the lake basin

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